

Heat discharge performance of metal hydride thermal battery under different heat transfer conditions: An experimental inquisitiveness

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The thermal batteries utilizing metal hydride pairs are gaining tremendous research attention for their applications in thermochemical energy storage. The pair consisting of a high-temperature metal hydride (HTMH; Mg-based hydride) and a low-temperature metal hydride (LTMH: AB₂ or AB₅ type hydride) is more appealing due to its relatively high energy storage density and medium energy storage efficiency, around 60-70 % [1]. However, the energy storage efficiency can be significantly increased by improving the heat discharge performance of the thermal battery. To accomplish this, heat should be provided to the LTMH bed to increase the operating gas pressure, thereby raising the temperature output from the HTMH. In this work, we experimentally explore the heat discharge performance of the MgH₂/(Ti-Zr)(Mn-Fe-Cr)₂-based thermal battery (Figure 1).

Figure 1. photographic representation of the test rig.

Figure 1 depicts the thermal battery connected to the test rig. Several thermocouples were placed in different locations in the reactors to monitor the local temperature changes during the heat discharge dynamics. Three configurations of the thermal battery were analyzed where the heat transfer conditions on the LTMH bed were varied. These heat transfer conditions include natural convection (config.1), forced convection (config.2), and resistive heating (config.3). Figure 2 summarizes the performance indicators of the thermal battery.

The results showed that when operating the LTMH bed under active heat transfer conditions (forced convection or resistive heating), the thermochemical energy storage density varies between 1500-1820 kJ/kg-Mg with relatively high-temperature

lift (heat upgrade) between 47-55 °C. On the other side, the thermal battery discharges heat at relatively high specific power ca. 100-225 W/kg-Mg, which can be beneficial to heat-to-work conversion applications.

Figure 2: Key performance indicators of the thermal battery during heat discharging process

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References

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